

Unraveling the Impact of Climate Change on Agriculture and Livestock: A Global Perspective

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Abstract

Global climate is undergoing continuous change, with projections indicating increasingly dynamic fluctuations in the coming years. The warming of the climate system is undeniable, and the substantial increase in average global temperatures is predominantly attributed to the profound impact of anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Climate change impacts will lead to changes in temperature, rainfall patterns, humidity, and atmospheric CO₂ level. These alterations will diminish water resources, decreased agricultural output, which ultimately affect the human and animals' livelihood. The climate system has experienced unparalleled transformations in recent decades, such as occurrences of droughts, floods, ocean acidification, rising sea levels, glacier melting, shifts in rainfall patterns, outbreaks of epidemic diseases, and challenges to food security. These modifications, coupled with other natural events triggered by climate change, have the potential to accelerate the extinction of numerous species and the degradation of their habitats. The livestock sector holds significant importance in agriculture, making substantial contributions to the nation's economy. This sector stands as the primary contributor, constituting 40% of the agricultural Gross Domestic Product (GDP) worldwide. India is the world's highest livestock owner at about 535.78 million livestock strength. In India Livestock provides livelihood to two-third of rural community and contributes 4.11% GDP and 25.6% of total Agriculture GDP. The performance and well-being of livestock will be directly impacted by climate change, primarily due to rising temperatures and the heightened occurrence of extreme weather events.

Key words: Climate change, Livestock, Epidemic diseases

The effect of climate change on cattle health

Climate change significantly affects the productive performance of livestock, including milk and meat production, and this could be attributed to the deviation of energy resources towards adaptive mechanisms. Livestock species can experience stress when exposed to temperature and humidity levels exceeding certain thresholds. Conditions where the temperature surpasses 25°C and the relative humidity is above 50% can have adverse effects on the functioning and productivity of animals. The persistent negative physiological impact of climate change, particularly heat stress, leads to substantial economic losses in the dairy industry.

Following are some altered physiological and biochemical processes inside animals' body for adapt to heat stress:

- Increased respiration rate,
- Profuse sweating,
- Increased core body temperature and skin temperature
- Reduced dry matter intake and metabolism
- Vasodilation of superficial blood vessels and increased blood flow
- Altered efficiency of feed utilization and water metabolism

Above adaptation strategies under climate change affect the immunity and gut microbiota, lead to further reduced in feed intake and it is hypothesized that to be an initially leading to lower milk production; it is often associated with negative energy balance, bodyweight loss, and high non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA) levels. When prolonged exposure to high air temperatures occurs, a decrease in feed intake is succeeded by a reduction in the secretion of calorogenic hormones, specifically growth hormone, catecholamines, and glucocorticoids. This affects thermogenic processes related to digestion, metabolism, and metabolic rate. Collectively, these event leads to lower feed intake, alterations in endocrine status, and a diminished metabolic rate which contribute to a decrease in metabolic heat production. This interplay may be accountable for changes in energy, lipids, protein, and mineral metabolism, as well as liver function.

Under climate change induced heat stress, cow's milk yield is significantly reduced and lower fat and protein concentrations. Reduction in milk production is one of the major economic impacts of climatic stress in dairy cattle. This impact on milk production is very severe on exotic breeds rather than on indigenous. Milk production is inhibited by heat stress through direct and indirect mechanisms and the average milk yield dropped by 2.2 kg per animal. Decreased synthesis of hepatic glucose and lower non-esterified fatty acid (NEFA) level in blood during heat stress causes reduced glucose supply to the mammary glands resulting in low lactose synthesis, which in turn follows low milk yield.

Cows experiencing heat stress also demonstrate alterations in post absorptive metabolism in the dry season, resulting in a subsequent decline in milk production to approximately 5–7.5 kg per day during the subsequent lactation period and it could result in huge economic loss. The dry period is an important phase for the involution of the mammary gland, during heat stress, down-regulation of Insulin like growth factor 1R (IGF 1R), which serves crucial role in mammary gland's cells growth. Despite the fact that cell loss predominates as involution advances and it's further impaired the ability of mammary glands to use nutrients and produce milk, which lead to reduce the milk quality and quantity in subsequent lactation. Heat stress might lead to a decrease in the protective benefits of colostrum

for both cows and pigs, as well as impacting the passive transfer of immunoglobulins in newborn calves.

The decline in productivity observed in cows experiencing heat stress primarily stems from a decrease in feed consumption, although elevated temperatures also directly influence reproductive physiology and altered defense mechanism of reproductive tract. High temperatures can lead to reduced fertility in dairy cows, as they may exhibit poor estrus expression due to decreased estradiol secretion from a dominant follicle, which develops in an environment with low luteinizing hormone levels. The productivity of dairy cows is adversely impacted by extended intervals between calving, resulting from a low conception rate (CR), prolonged sexual inactivity after giving birth, and insufficient expression of estrus.

Diseases of dairy cattle associated with climate change

Infectious diseases especially vector-borne diseases and diseases having a stage in the environment are likely to be more affected by climate change than other diseases.

Mastitis

Environmental infections thrive in the hot and humid conditions of summer like seasonal influences on the incidence rate of clinical mastitis caused by several infections have been recorded. The incidence rate of Clinical mastitis caused by *Streptococcus uberis* reached its peak during the summer, whereas infections from other pathogens like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Streptococcus dysgalactiae* were more prone to occur during the winter. The high temperatures may facilitate survival and multiplication of pathogens or their vectors, or a negative action of heat stress on defensive mechanisms.

Metritis

The frequency of metritis in cattle may show an increasing pattern during periods of heat stress. Experiencing heat stress in the latter phases of gestation has the capability to hinder uterine defense mechanisms, thereby playing a role in the development of uterine disorders like metritis. This state can lead to reduced fertilization rates, compromised early embryonic development, and an increased risk of pregnancy loss.

Mycotoxicosis

The impact of climate change on livestock health is manifested through the

positive influence of elevated temperatures and humidity on the proliferation of mycotoxin-producing fungi. Concerning alterations in animal well-being, mycotoxins can induce acute episodes of illness when animals ingest significant amounts of these toxins. Distinct toxins can have targeted effects on specific organs or tissues, including the liver, kidneys, oral and gastric mucosa, brain, or reproductive tract. In instances of acute mycotoxicoses, the symptoms of the disease are typically pronounced and directly linked to the specific organs affected. At lower levels, mycotoxins diminish the growth rate of young animals, and certain ones disrupt inherent resistance mechanisms and hinder immunologic responsiveness, rendering the animals more vulnerable to infections. Research indicates that specific mycotoxins can modify lymphocyte function in domestic ruminants by affecting the structure and function of DNA.

Hemorrhagic septicemia

Instances after abundant rainfall have been noted to result in widespread occurrences of HS in buffalo population and causes huge economic losses to livestock holder.

Vector borne diseases

Elevated temperatures could accelerate the growth of pathogens or parasites that spend some of their life cycle outside their animal host, which may lead to larger populations. Weather and climate alterations that may impact the spread of diseases carried by vectors encompass changes in temperature, rainfall, wind patterns, and occurrences of extreme flooding or drought. Various consequences of climate change on disease vectors, such as midges, flies, ticks, mosquitoes, and tsetse, which play crucial roles in transmitting livestock diseases in tropical regions, include alterations in both their geographical range and population levels. Shifts in rainfall and temperature patterns, along with variations in the occurrence of extreme events, can influence the distribution and prevalence of these vectors, impacting the outbreak dynamics of diseases transmitted by mosquitoes, among other factors. Higher temperatures may lead to an elevated frequency of feeding among arthropod vectors. Since many of these vectors require two feeding sessions on appropriate hosts for transmission to occur (first to acquire the infection and then to transmit it), warmer temperatures could enhance the probability of successful disease transmission.

- **Cattle trypanosomiasis**

Changes in the environment due to climate can affect where tsetse flies' lives, mainly clearing bushes are probably play more significant role in tsetse flies to reproduce and increase risk of transmission of trypanosomiasis in cattle and equine.

- **Blue tongue**

Bluetongue disease, a fatal viral infection for sheep and other ruminants, is transmitted by *Culicoides spp.* Instances of drought followed by abundant rainfall have been noted to result in widespread occurrences of bluetongue diseases, because of increase population of *culicoides* and enhances survivability of virus in the vector in warmer climate.

- **Lumpy skin disease**

Lumpy skin disease (LSD) is a viral infection that primarily affects cattle, causing skin nodules and other symptoms. Climate-related factors, such as rising temperatures and changing precipitation patterns, may influence the distribution and prevalence of the disease. Climate change can potentially create more favorable conditions for the vectors (insects) transmitting the virus, impacting the geographic spread and intensity of lumpy skin disease in certain regions.

Strategies for managing dairy cattle health in the changing climate

The livestock industries are significantly impacted by climate change, affecting production, reproduction, animal health, input costs, product prices, and the management of natural resources. For combating the climate impact on livestock sector different following strategies can be applied:

- **Improvised housing system**

Animal housing is one of the approaches to alleviate the impacts of climate change on cattle. Shade reduces the severity of heat stress in animals that are being exposed to sun. Shades can be made artificial or natural. Aluminum or galvanized steel roofs are artificial shades while the roofs made out of straw are of natural means. Roofing material is a bad conductor of heat and the best housing will have roofs painted in white so as to reflect the radiation of sun. Planting trees and introducing additional vegetation in the vicinity can mitigate the impact of radiative heat load on cattle. To prevent the sunlight from directly entering the shed, it's best to position it in a north-south direction if you're in the northern hemisphere. Increasing the ventilation of house by means such as keeping half side wall

(open housing system) introduce fan and sprinklers, increasing the height of the building etc. for effective heat dissipation in cattle by providing free flow of air inside the shed.

Water and air circulation play crucial roles in cooling the microenvironment within the barn, and the cooling effect is enhanced by the evaporative cooling from the animals. Reducing heat stress involves improving heat dissipation using sprinklers, misters, or foggers, alongside fans and the use of air conditioners, especially in extremely hot climates. Sprinkling of water on pen surfaces is also more beneficial than sprinkling on the animal. Reducing the stocking density per shed during hot weather aids in more effective dissipation of body heat, while in cold conditions, the stocking density can be raised.

- **Nutritional support**

For dairy cows, water, the most crucial nutrient, should be easily accessible, clean, and cool to encourage consumption. When the temperature rises to 80°F, cows tend to drink 50% more water compared to when it's 40°F. This means their daily intake, which is typically around 30 gallons, might increase to 45 gallons or even more. Cooling drinking water to 50°F reduces heat stress, leading to lower respiration and rectal temperatures. This, in turn, promotes higher feed intake, increased rumen motility, and enhanced milk yield.

In the hot, dry climate, a decline in dietary feed intake occurs, leading to a decrease in productivity. Changes in diet are needed during hot weather to maintain nutrient intake in order to maintain homeostasis. In this condition, effective and practical strategies are necessary, such as providing frequent feed, enhancing the quality of forage, utilizing palatable feeds, ensuring a balanced nutrition, and increasing nutrient density. Due to the increased heat production linked to the metabolism of acetate in comparison to propionate, it makes sense to feed low-fiber rations during hot weather. The loss of minerals through sweating, particularly potassium, and alterations in blood acid-base chemistry caused by hyperventilation lead to a reduction in blood bicarbonate and buffering capacity. This, in turn, increases the urinary excretion of electrolytes. Consequently, supplementing electrolytes becomes essential. Cattle experience lower heat production when fed with ingredients like concentrates and fats, as opposed to forages which have a higher heat increment. Furthermore, a diet rich in fiber results in the production of more acetate, which

contributes to a greater heat during nutrient metabolism compared to propionate. Diets for lactating cows that include grains and have low fiber content generate less heat stress due to their lower heat of digestion. Nonetheless, it is important to provide high-quality roughages to avoid the risk of acidosis.

Including antioxidants in cow diets is an effective method for stress reduction and serves as a valuable strategy to prevent mastitis. This approach also optimizes feed intake and mitigates the adverse effects of heat stress on milk production. Antioxidants like Vitamin E, Vitamin A, selenium, and selenium-enriched yeast play a crucial role in minimizing the impact of heat stress on the oxidant balance, leading to enhanced milk quality and overall cow health

- **Reproductive management**

Use of modern reproductive technologies like Estrus synchronization, embryo transfer, hormone assay, ultrasonic imaging are of potential applications and useful in managing climate change related reproductive disturbances. Estrus synchronization provides an opportunity for improved planning of breeding activities and more extensive utilization of Artificial insemination (AI). This can improve estrous detection rates. Using prostaglandin F_{2α} for synchronization was effective when cows were bred during identified estrus, as it led to increased rates of estrus detection and more efficient management of artificial insemination compared to daily estrus detection. Several strategies for managing and mitigating the effects of climate change include controlling temperature and humidity, providing mineral and vitamin supplements, utilizing embryo transfer, and employing hormonal therapy. To alleviate the impact of heat stress on fertility, measures such as providing shade, using fans, installing air-conditioning, and employing sprinkler systems can be effective in cooling animals. The utilization of embryo transfer can circumvent the adverse impacts of heat stress on oocyte quality, which otherwise hinders embryonic development.

Reduced plasma concentrations of LH and estradiol in heat-stressed cows are significant factors leading to decreased fertility during the warmer months. Employing reproductive hormones to enhance fertility serves as an alternative strategy for improving reproductive success during the warmer climate. Supplementing antioxidants can elevate the

occurrences of estrus, boost fertilization rates, enhance conception rates, and prevent dystocia and other complications in the reproductive tract.

- **Health management**

To prevent, monitor, and control livestock diseases, a robust data exchange mechanism is essential at both state and national levels. This system should encompass information on the prevalence of animal diseases, ecological conditions including climate, and the availability of drugs and chemotherapeutants. Epidemiological surveillance plays a crucial role, encompassing not only the early detection of emerging diseases and trends but also serving as a tool for resource planning and assessing the effectiveness of control strategies in forecasted climates related diseases. A comprehensive global strategy for epidemiological surveillance is necessary, involving cooperation among professionals in human, animal, and environmental health. These surveillance programs are vital for identifying and responding to emerging risks associated with climate change. The use of Geographic Information System (GIS) allows us to observe the degree of stress and changes in our climate and also track the spread of diseases. This system tells us which pathogens will flourish, under their preferred condition. GIS also help to pinpoint period of continually high minimum temperature. Predictive modeling systems can be applied to anticipate the likelihood of an outcome, holding the potential to predict the probability of global climate change's impact on ecological systems and the emergence of hazards.

Based on all these prediction studies authorities established the prevention and control measures of forecasted disease.

Conclusion

Climate change is poised to influence animal health, and infectious diseases will be no exception. The global distribution and incidence of vector-borne diseases (VBD) will be impacted by climate change, with varying effects across different regions. Current evidence suggests that certain diseases may already be experiencing climate-related impacts. However, risk assessments are challenging due to the complex transmission cycles and multiple factors involved. Potential consequences include the unexpected emergence of new pathogens or diseases and the re-emergence of existing ones. Evaluating the risk of potential diseases involves identifying potential pathogens and routes of

disease spread, allowing for the prediction of disease-prone areas. Implementing surveillance efforts to monitor disease spread and planning interventions can help reduce the risk of animal diseases. Despite existing knowledge gaps, ongoing research holds the potential to fill these gaps in the near future.

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